

DETERMINATION OF VITAMINS IN THE COMPOSITION OF EXTRACTS OF LICHENES “DERMATOCARPON MINIATUM LINNAEUS” AND “PELTIGERA CANINA LINNAEUS”

¹Ismoilova Sh.S., ²Abdurakhmanova U.K.

^{1,2}Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14580517>

Abstract. *The article prepared extracts of lichens “Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus”, “Peltigera canina linnaeus” and studied their chemical composition. The content of physiologically active vitamins (V1, V2, V9, V12, C, and PP) in the thick extracts of lichens was studied by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). As a result, due to the fact that water-soluble vitamins in the extract of the plants “Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus”, “Peltigera canina linnaeus” went into solution together with phenolic compounds, absorption spectra characteristic of vitamins (B6, PP, B12, B2) were observed in the spectrum, which was determined by comparison with the chromatogram of the vitamin standard.*

Keywords: *lichens, “Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus”, “Peltigera canina linnaeus”, extract, vitamins, YSSX method, acetonitrile, acetic acid, sodium hydroxide.*

Introduction Many biologically active and nutritive substances extracted from plants are widely used in various sectors of the national economy, such as pharmaceuticals, folk medicine, and the food industry. Since ancient times, folk medicine has paid special attention to medicinal plants with anti-infective properties. When medicines used to treat human diseases are obtained from natural plants, they are harmless and have a wide range of effects. One of such medicinal plants is lichens, and one of the components that give them medicinal properties is vitamins. Vitamins are formed from complex organic compounds and are found in all organs of plants. They are very resistant to the effects of the external environment, quickly deteriorate, decompose, and lose their beneficial properties. For example, C, P, V1, V2, PP, N, and pathogenic vitamins quickly decompose in boiling water and lose their healing properties. Vitamins A, D, E do not decompose or break down quickly in boiling water, but they decompose in fats and lose their properties. Vitamins C, A, V, are destroyed by the action of oxygen. Vitamin B2 is more resistant to the effects, the vitamin is considered a permanent and necessary component for human tissues and actively participates in the metabolic process. It increases the ability of the human body to protect itself from various diseases. It prevents the accumulation of cholesterol on the walls of blood vessels. It is also important in maintaining the constant composition of the blood. They play an important role in metabolism, the functioning of the human brain and nervous system, preventing blood clotting, and the development of the immune system. In short, no process in the human body takes place without the participation of trace elements.

The healing properties of lichens are associated with their chemical composition, that is, they are determined by the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, vitamins, carbohydrates and other biologically active substances. The chemical composition and healing properties of lichens have not been studied in our country to date, therefore, expanding research in this area, developing new types of drugs, studying their chemical composition, and studying the structures of the obtained

compounds based on modern physicochemical methods and studying their biological activity are among the urgent problems of chemistry.

The purpose of this research is to study the chemical composition of the lichen extracts of “*Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus*”, “*Peltigera canina linnaeus*” and to isolate vitamins from their extracts, determine the physicochemical properties of the extracted substance, and study its quantitative composition using the YuSSX analysis methods.

Experimental part

Used reagents and methods.

In the study, the following method was used to qualitatively and quantitatively determine the flavonoids in finely ground samples of lichens “*Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus*”, “*Peltigera canina linnaeus*”:

70% ethyl alcohol was used as a solvent to extract the substances to be determined from the sample. 96% and 70% ethanol were used as solvents to conduct the research. Reagents such as YSXX grade (bidistillate) water, acetonitrile, chemically pure acetic acid and sodium hydroxide (k.t.) were used.

Samples of plants “*Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus*”, “*Peltigera canina linnaeus*” were mixed with 20 ml of ethyl alcohol in an ultrasonic bath (GT SONIC-D3 (China) brand) and extracted for 75 minutes at 30°C using a magnetic stirrer. The process of constant mixing of the mixtures was carried out on a magnetic stirrer (MM-5 TU 25-11834-80 model). Then they were centrifuged in a Mini-7 brand (BIOBASE, China) centrifuge (at a speed of 7000 rpm). Analytical balances with an accuracy of 0.01 g (OHAUS (USA) NV222) were used. The content of vitamins in the plant was determined on a LC 2030 C 3D Plus high-performance liquid chromatograph manufactured by Shimadzu, Japan.

Discussion of the obtained results

The following results were obtained in the chromatographic analysis of the extract composition of the plant samples “*Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus*”, “*Peltigera canina linnaeus*”.

Since water-soluble vitamins in the plant extract dissolved together with phenolic compounds, absorption spectra characteristic of vitamins (B6, PP, B12, B2) were observed in the spectrum, which was determined by comparing it with the chromatogram of the vitamin standard:

The qualitative and quantitative indicators of vitamins B1 (47858), B2 (47864), B6 (80823-50MG), Vitamin B9 (PHR1035-1G), B12 (PHR1234-1), C (47863) and PP (47865-U) in the finely ground samples were determined using a YSSX LC 2030 C 3D Plus device manufactured in Japan (Shimadzu) with a PDA detector at selected wavelengths of 260, 290 and 361 nm. A C18 250x4.6 mm 5 µm Precise (Perkin Elmer) USA column was used as the stationary phase. Vitamin analysis was performed using a 0.5% acetic acid solution as the A phase and acetonitrile as the B phase in a variable mode.

The content of vitamins B1 (47858), B2 (47864), B6 (80823-50MG), Vitamin B9 (PHR1035-1G), B12 (PHR1234-1), C (47863) and PP (47865-U) in finely ground plant samples was determined qualitatively and quantitatively using standard samples (Sigma Aldrich, Germany) using a PDA detector at 260, 290 and 361 nm wavelengths. A C18 250x4.6 mm 5 µm Precise (Perkin Elmer) USA column was used as the stationary phase. In the analysis of vitamins, a 0.5% solution of acetic acid was used as the mobile phase, phase A and phase B of acetonitrile were used as the mobile phase (Table 2).

Table 2

Phase change mode in the analysis of vitamins

Time min	Phase A %, 0.5% solution of acetic acid in water	Phase B %, Acetonitrile
0,1	96	4
4	90	10
8	85	15
12	60	40
14	Stop	

The flow rate was 1 ml/min, the thermostat temperature was 400C, the injected sample volume was 10 µl, and the analysis time was 14 minutes.

The sample taken for the extraction of vitamins in the sample was weighed on an analytical balance of 1 g (FA220 4N) with an accuracy of 0.001 mg. Then, it was treated with 20 ml of 0.1 N hydrochloric acid solution, stirred on a magnetic stirrer at 1210C for 60 min, then the solution was centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 10 min and filtered through a 0.45 µm filter and placed in a vial. After the samples were ready, the following chromatograms were obtained (Figures 3-4).

Figure 3 Chromatogram of standard samples of vitamins B1, B2, B6, B9, B12, C and PP.

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 260nm							
Peak#	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Unit	Mark	Name
1	2,415	1441972	230749	73,117	mg/L	V	Vitamin B1
2	3,048	171586	27182	39,621	mg/L	V	Vitamin C
4	4,472	4349156	623894	223,262	mg/L	V	Vitamin PP
Total		5962713	881824				

PDA Ch2 290nm							
Peak#	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Unit	Mark	Name
5	3,759	1294453	173203	45,421	mg/L	S	Vitamin B6
Total		1294453	173203				

PDA Ch3 361nm							
Peak#	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Unit	Mark	Name
1	9,873	77897	12784	11,976	mg/L		Vitamin B9
3	11,387	178234	28057	19,040	mg/L		Vitamin B12
5	12,602	506577	112805	42,236	mg/L		Vitamin B2
Total		762708	153646				

The concentrated extracts were quantitatively analyzed in the YSSX. The presence and amount of vitamins B1 (23.96 mg/kg), B2 (11.72 mg/kg), B9 (218.72 mg/kg), B12 (48.92 mg/kg), C (258.9 mg/kg), and PP (157.36 mg/kg) were determined in the extract of “*Peltigera canina linnaeus*”, vitamin B6 was not found in the extract.

The presence and amount of vitamins B2 (107.24 mg/kg), B9 (66.076 mg/kg), B12 (62.96 mg/kg), C (644.06 mg/kg), PP (966.1 mg/kg) were determined in the extract of “*Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus*”, vitamin B1 and vitamin B6 were not found in the extract. It was found that the highest number of vitamins in the composition of “*Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus*” corresponds to vitamins PP and C (Table 3).

Table 3

The number of vitamins in the extract (mg/100g of dry mass)

	Vitamin B ₁ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₂ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₆ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₁₂ (mg/kg)	Vitamin B ₉ (mg/kg)	Vitamin PP (mg/kg)	Vitamin C (mg/kg)
“ <i>Peltigera canina linnaeus</i> ”	23,96	11,72	0	48,92	218,72	157,36	258,9
“ <i>Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus</i> ”	0	107,24	0	62,96	66,076	966,1	644,06

<Chromatogram>
mV

Figure 4. Chromatogram of vitamins in the extract of the plant “*Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus*”.

Conclusion. Flavonoids and vitamins in the extract of lichen samples “*Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus*”, “*Peltigera canina linnaeus*” were isolated by extraction method, their quantity was determined by YSSX method and chromatograms were compared with standards and studied. A method was developed to determine the quantitative value of quercetin, apigenin, kaempferol flavonoids, as well as vitamins B1, B2, B9, B12, C, and PP in the extract of lichen samples. Rutin and gallic acids were not detected in the extracts of both lichens studied. The amount of macro- and microelements necessary for normal life of lichens *Dermatocarpon miniatum linnaeus*, *Peltigera canina linnaeus* was studied by ISP-OES method, and it was found that calcium and potassium elements are present in the largest amount in them.

REFERENCES

1. Гуларьянц Г. [Хрупкий мир лишайников](#) // [Наука и жизнь](#). - 2017. - № 11. - С. 112-117.
2. Флора лишайников России: Биология, экология, разнообразие, распространение и методы изучения лишайников / Отв. ред. М. П. Андреев, Д. Е. Гимельбрант. — М.; СПб.: Товарищество научных изданий КМК, 2014. — 392 с.

3. М.П.Андреев М.П.Биологическое разнообразие лишайников Русской Арктики (таксономический состав и предварительный анализ) / Андреев М.П., Котлов Ю.В., Макарова И.И. // *Новости систематики низших растений*. т. 31. 1996. С. 82 – 94.
4. [O‘zME](#). Birinchi jild. Toshkent, 2000-yil.
5. Селиванов А.Е. Лишайники заповедников «Басеги» и «Вишерский» (Пермская область) // *Новости систематики низших растений*. 2005. Т. 38.
6. Пауков А.Г.Новые для флоры Урала виды литофильных лишайников / А.Г.Пауков, С.Н.Трапезникова // *Бот. журн.* – 2003. – Т. 88. – № 2. – С. 104 – 109.
7. Xu, M.S.; Chen, S.; Wang, W.Q.; Liu, S.Q. Employing bifunctional enzymes for enhanced extraction of bioactives from plants: Flavonoids as an example. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 2013, 61, 7941–7948.
8. Zuiter, A.S.; Zarqa, J. Proanthocyanidin: Chemistry and biology: From phenolic compounds to proanthocyanidins. In *Reference Module in Chemistry, Molecular Sciences and Chemical Engineering*; Reedijk, J., Ed.; Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2014; -pp.1-29.
9. Karabin, M.; Hudcova, T.; Jelinek, L.; Dostalek, P. Biotransformation and biological activities of hop flavonoids. *Biotech. Adv.* 2015, 33, 1063–1090.
10. Sharma, V.; Janmeda, P. Extraction, isolation and identification of flavonoid from *Euphorbia neriifolia* leaves. *AJC* 2017, 10, 509–514.
11. Arora, S.; Itankar, P. Extraction, isolation and identification of flavonoid from *Chenopodium album* aerial parts. *JTCM* 2018, 8, 476–482.
12. De Villiers, A.; Venter, P.; Pasch, H. Recent advances and trends in the liquid-chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis of flavonoids. *J. Chromatogr. A* 2016, 1430, 16–78.
13. Olgaray, K.E.; Bradford, B.J. Plant flavonoids to improve productivity of ruminants—A review. *Anim. Feed Sci. Tech.* 2019, 251, 21–36.